

Research Paper

Numerical modeling of an auger reactor for biomass pyrolysis using a coupled DEM–CFD model

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ABSTRACT

Biomass pyrolysis is a process of significant importance for the production of bio-gas, bio-oil, and biochar. The operating parameters strongly affect the composition and quality of the resulting products. Numerical models enable the analysis of the influence of operating parameters on the process. This study focuses on the numerical modeling of biomass pyrolysis in an auger reactor. A coupled Discrete Element Method–Computational Fluid Dynamics (DEM–CFD) approach was employed, where the gas phase was simulated using ANSYS Fluent software, and the biomass bed was modeled with ANSYS Rocky. The two models were integrated through two-way coupling method. A devolatilization model based on three kinetic reactions was implemented in the DEM framework, with kinetic parameters determined from Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) measurements of biomass samples. The developed model enables the simulation of the temperature field within the bed and the analysis of heat transfer conditions influence to biomass devolatilization. Validation was performed against experimental data obtained in a laboratory-scale pyrolysis setup for different residence times and reactor filling levels. The simulation results showed good agreement with the measurements, while also highlighting the need for further model refinement and development. The proposed method provides a useful tool for reactor design and scale-up, enabling prediction and control of product quality in terms of non-uniformity.

1. Introduction

Biomass, like other renewable energy sources, represents an important alternative to fossil fuels. Biofuels such as biogas and bio-oil can be produced by pyrolysis in reactors designed for this purpose. Physical and chemical properties of products obtained in this way are influenced by many factors, such as properties of the raw material (feedstock), operating conditions and the design of the reactor itself.

Many types of reactors can be used for biomass processing, including fluidized bed, rotating cone, cyclone, vortex, auger, and other reactors [1,2]. All of these designs have specific advantages and disadvantages in terms of construction complexity, operating conditions, and operational costs. The auger reactor concept was chosen here due to its simplicity and common use in lab-scale pyrolysis.

Campuzano et al. [3] and Brassard et al. [4] conducted wide reviews of pyrolysis technologies based on auger reactors. They concluded that auger pyrolyzers can be used for a wide range of feedstocks, including biomass and waste. They can be used not only for fast pyrolysis but also for slow and intermediate processes that can be problematic with

other technologies. The auger reactors are characterized by a simple design and can be scaled up to higher capacities, making them useful in industrial applications. Additionally, using these reactors, operating conditions can be varied to obtain different yields and desired product properties. However, a drawback of current auger reactors is the lack of clear scaling rules for bringing the laboratory and pilot scale systems to the industrial scale, and the achievement of similar performance and product properties [4,5]. In the work of Funke et al. [5], dimensional analysis was used to evaluate the possibility of developing scaling rules for a fast pyrolysis auger reactors, but the authors concluded that there is no simple scaling methodology based on dimensionless numbers. Numerical modeling may be a good approach to scaling reactors, however, it is necessary to develop a model that allows for the most accurate possible representation of the physical and chemical processes occurring in the reactor, including the level of individual particles.

Many parameters significantly influence the pyrolysis process in the reactor, starting from design features such as dimensions or the

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pitch of the screw conveyor, to process parameters such as feeding rate or heating strategy. The reactor can include multiple zones with different temperature levels and varying material movement speeds. The feeding rate affects the feedstock filling level, which impacts the intensity of heat transfer and consequently the parameters of the final products [6,7]. The construction of an auger reactor, consisting of a rotating screw and side walls that typically include insulation and heating elements, poses challenges in obtaining measurement data from inside the device. Obtaining information about the structure of the particle bed inside is difficult. In this context, as well as in the design of the entire reactor, the use of numerical modeling methods can be helpful. These methods enable predictions of particle behavior and process parameters such as residence time or temperature distribution. This is particularly relevant when scaling up screw reactors from the laboratory to the industrial scale, which is essential for pyrolysis technology to be economically viable. The specific biomass throughput is limited by the thermodynamic conditions. The ratio of heated surface area to reactor volume is particularly relevant here. However, the behavior of the biomass in the screw reactor also affects this. This can only be determined experimentally to a minimal extent; therefore, numerical modeling can support the findings regarding the upscaling of screw reactors [8].

An example of the practical application of an auger reactor is the TCR (Thermo-Catalytic Reforming) developed by Fraunhofer UMSICHT in Germany. The installation is described in [9] and the pyrolytic reactor is one of its components. TCR combines pyrolysis with post-catalytic treatment to produce bio-oil and biochar. The auger reactor features zones with different pyrolysis temperatures, and the residence time in each zone plays a key role in determining the proportions and composition of the resulting products. At the same time, such a design poses a challenge when it comes to optimizing operating parameters and upscaling. The authors point out the need to develop a commercial-scale device with a capacity that meets market demands. Numerical modeling can support this process by enabling the prediction of temperature profiles and particle residence times in different sections of the reactor.

Many numerical models have been developed to predict the behavior of auger reactors. They differ considerably in their approach to modeling of the multiphase flow, in complexity, and computational time required to obtain the solution. Processes occurring in the auger pyrolyzer can be described as reactive granular flow, which includes two-phase gas–particle flow, heat transfer, and thermochemical conversion of feedstock. The most common methods used in CFD modeling of moving particle beds are the Eulerian–Eulerian and Eulerian–Lagrangian approaches. In the Eulerian–Eulerian models, also known as multi-fluid approach, the two phases are treated as interpenetrating continua and are described with separate mass, momentum, and energy equations. The Kinetic Theory of Granular Flow (KTGF) is typically used to describe the interactions in the solid phase. A major limitation of KTGF for modeling of biomass beds is that it should not be applied to highly dense and cohesive granular systems (which is the case of the biomass bed in an auger reactor). The fundamentals of this approach can be found in [10]. In the Euler–Lagrange methodology, the gas phase is treated as continuous, while the solid phase is composed of discrete particles, whose movement is described by Newton's laws of motion [11]. Additional sub-models are needed for drag, collisions, heat transfer and other phenomena like chemical reactions. In this approach, particle interactions can be modeled in two general ways. In the first one, particles are treated as points with no volume, and the interactions between them are modeled based on KTGF. Usually, one point in the model represents a group of real particles. The second model is the Discrete Element Method (DEM), where all particles in the system are represented in the model, including their volume, and particle–particle interactions are resolved explicitly. The DEM model is the most accurate way of modeling dense granular flows among the above-mentioned approaches, but at the same time it is the most

computationally demanding, especially for large systems with a large number of particles [12].

Aramideh et al. [13] performed CFD simulations of biomass fast pyrolysis in an auger reactor. In their work, the Eulerian–Eulerian approach was used. Pyrolysis process was included in the model based on a multistep kinetic mechanism. The authors used BIOTC code developed within the framework of OpenFOAM CFD code. The model was validated using measurement data, and the CFD predictions agreed well with the experimental data, however conversion of the biomass was underestimated. The authors noticed that rotation of the screw caused swirling of solid phase in the model, what should not occur in a real reactor, and led to increased contact between biomass and heated walls. A similar approach was used by Jalalifar et al. [14] and Shi et al. [15]; however, the authors used Ansys Fluent code instead. In the work by Jalalifar et al. [14], the model predictions were in good agreement with experimental data, and only oil yield was overpredicted by around 15%. The model developed by Shi et al. [15] well predicted the temperature profile, as well as the product yields during pyrolysis process in the reactor. Based on the described studies, it can be concluded that the Eulerian–Eulerian model is a sufficient approach to predict product yields and temperature during the pyrolysis process in auger reactors; however, it cannot give information about behavior of single particles in the bed. It also becomes difficult when it is necessary to include particle size distribution or particles of different types (for example, reacting and filling particles). Therefore, existing models without a DEM coupling are limited in their transferability to actual systems [8].

Qi et al. [16] used the DEM method for simulation of fast pyrolysis in a double auger reactor fed with biomass and sand particles. To simplify the computation process, the authors assumed that the analyzed particles were spherical. A multi-component fast pyrolysis kinetics was adopted in the model. Convective and radiative heat transfer were also included for interparticle interactions. The predicted product yields satisfactorily agreed with the experimental data. The DEM model was not coupled with the CFD model, and therefore the influence of the flowing gas was not analyzed. The coupled DEM–CFD method was used in work of Wang et al. [17]. The authors investigated the pyrolysis of biomass in a mechanical fluidized bed reactor, which is a vertical reactor with a screw moving the particles upwards. The effect of rotation speed on heating rate, as well as heating uniformity, were analyzed. To achieve this, the conductive, convective, and radiative heat transfer were included in the model. The first-order kinetic reaction was used to describe the pyrolysis process of biomass. To validate the numerical model, experiments were carried out, including fixed-bed and moving-bed reactors. The applied research method allowed for visualization of particle mixing in the reactor and for determining temperature evolutions with high accuracy demonstrating the usefulness of the DEM–CFD method in modeling of moving biomass beds.

In the review article, Attanayake [18] highlights, among other points, that accounting for particle non-sphericity in numerical simulations of pyrolysis reactors remains one of the open challenges in the analysis and modeling of such systems. Authors also point out the lack of more detailed analyses, such as DEM–CFD studies, for certain reactor designs, including auger reactors. In this study, the coupled DEM–CFD method was used for the first time to model a horizontal auger reactor. Moreover, unlike in previous studies, the model incorporates the actual cylindrical shape of biomass particles (pellets), which affects the particle movement within the reactor as well as the heating process, since the contact surface between the particles and the reactor walls, as well as between the particles themselves, changes. The shape also affects the ratio of external surface area to the volume and the distribution of particles within the reactor, which in turn influences the residence time and pyrolysis rate. Thus, the present work addresses several of the research gaps identified in the literature and provides a more physically consistent description of the coupled particle dynamics and heat transfer in auger reactors. Additionally, this work systematically analyzes the influence of operating conditions on temperature and mass loss non-uniformity within the reactor and at its outlet, fully exploiting the capabilities of the DEM–CFD framework for reactor design and scale-up support.

Fig. 1. Test stand schematic with the most important components highlighted.

2. Test stand description and experimental procedure

The test stand used during the experiments was a custom-built setup that included a screw feeder placed inside an electric tube furnace, as shown in Fig. 1.

The screw was driven by a motor with an adjustable rotation speed, allowing control over the residence time of the sample within the heated zone. The particles were fed into the reactor using a feeder placed above the front section of the auger. The devolatilized solid products of pyrolysis were collected at the furnace outlet in the sample collector and remained there until they were cooled down to avoid oxidation due to contact with atmospheric air. Nitrogen N_2 was supplied both into the heating zone and the sample collector to ensure an inert atmosphere suitable for pyrolysis. A series of four pyrolysis experiments was conducted to evaluate the thermal decomposition behavior of biomass pellets under varying process conditions. Two different sample portion masses were tested: 0.0235 kg and 0.0564 kg. For each sample, residence times of 6 and 12 min within the heated zone of the furnace were applied, resulting in a total of four experimental conditions. During the measurements, the samples were fed into the reactor in several equal portions every 2 min for a case with residence time of 6 min, and every 4 min for a residence time of 12 min. The furnace temperature was maintained at a constant level of 500°C throughout all tests to simulate the typical operational conditions of large-scale pyrolysis systems. In the initial experiments that included 0.0235 kg samples, the nitrogen flow rate was set at 0.11 m³/h to ensure an inert atmosphere. However, in the 12-minute residence time case, the presence of ash in the pyrolysis residue indicated a possible oxygen infiltration into the reaction chamber. To mitigate this, the N_2 flow rate was increased to 1.0 m³/h for all subsequent tests to maintain strictly anaerobic conditions and the case with the 12-minute residence time was repeated. All the next experiments were conducted with 1.0 m³/h flow of nitrogen.

The biomass used in this study was birch pellets. The particles had a diameter of 4.2 mm and an average length of 12 mm. The physical parameters are listed in Table 1. The density and friction coefficients were determined experimentally, while the specific heat capacity and thermal conductivity were estimated based on [19].

To obtain representative average samples for analysis, each experimental condition was repeated multiple times, with the respective sample portions loaded into the furnace in several runs. The solid pyrolysis products collected at the outlet were submitted to an external laboratory for analysis (Table 2). The volatile matter content of raw biomass decreased significantly after pyrolysis under all tested conditions. For the 0.0235 kg samples, an increase in residence time from 6 min (Case 1) to 12 min (Case 2) resulted in a pronounced reduction in volatile matter, indicating a more complete devolatilization process.

Table 1

Physical parameters of pellet material.

Parameter	Unit	Value
Density	kg/m ³	705
Specific heat capacity	J/(kgK)	1900
Thermal conductivity	W/(mK)	0.3
Static friction coefficient	–	0,62
Dynamic friction coefficient	–	0,55

A similar trend was observed for the 0.0564 kg samples, where volatile matter decreased from 32.2% daf (dry ash-free) after 6 min (Case 3) to 28.1% daf after 12 min (Case 4). The mass loss of volatiles is a key parameter for developing and validating mathematical models of biomass pyrolysis, as it directly influences predictions of gas yield, char composition, and process energy balance.

3. Mathematical model

The behavior of particles in the reactor was modeled using DEM approach implemented in Ansys Rocky software. This model was coupled with CFD model developed in Ansys Fluent using 2-way coupling procedure, where particles data (volume fraction, temperature) are transferred to CFD model and parameters of continuous phase are transferred from CFD model to Rocky in order to determine gas–particle interactions. In DEM method equations of motion are numerically integrated in time for individual particles. Particle displacement is calculated based on forces acting on it, including interactions with surfaces and other particles. In case of coupled DEM–CFD model also the drag force needs to be included. The force and torque balance can be written as [20]:

$$m_p \frac{d\mathbf{v}_p}{dt} = \mathbf{F}_c + \mathbf{F}_{fp} + \mathbf{F}_g \quad (1)$$

$$J_p \frac{d\boldsymbol{\omega}_p}{dt} = \mathbf{M}_c + \mathbf{M}_{fp} \quad (2)$$

where m_p is mass of the particle, J_p is moment of inertia of the particle, \mathbf{v}_p is translational velocity, $\boldsymbol{\omega}_p$ is angular velocity, \mathbf{F}_c represents contact forces accounting from particle–particle and wall–particle interactions, \mathbf{F}_{fp} is a drag force acting from fluid, \mathbf{F}_g is a gravitational force, \mathbf{M}_c is the net torque generated by tangential forces, \mathbf{M}_{fp} is a torque due to the fluid phase velocity gradient. The contact force is the vector sum of two components—the normal force and the tangential force.

$$\mathbf{F}_c = \mathbf{F}_n + \mathbf{F}_{tan} \quad (3)$$

Hysteretic linear spring model proposed by Walton and Braun [21] was used to calculate normal force. This model is described by the

Table 2
Results of the proximate analysis of biomass samples obtained during the experiment.

Parameters	Standard	Unit	State	Raw biomass	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4
Total moisture	PN-EN ISO 18134-2:2017-03	%	ar	7.7 ± 0.2	1.9 ± 0.1	2.2 ± 0.1	2.0 ± 0.1	2.1 ± 0.1
Ash	PN-EN ISO	%	db	3.5 ± 0.2	9.9 ± 0.6	10.7 ± 0.7	6.8 ± 0.4	7.5 ± 0.5
	18122:2023-05	%	ar	3.2 ± 0.2	9.7 ± 0.7	10.5 ± 0.7	6.7 ± 0.5	7.3 ± 0.5
Volatile matter	PN-EN ISO	%	db	79.4 ± 3.5	33.8 ± 1.5	28.1 ± 1.3	30.0 ± 1.3	26.0 ± 1.2
	18123:2023-10	%	ar	73.3 ± 3.7	33.2 ± 1.7	27.5 ± 1.4	29.4 ± 1.5	25.5 ± 1.3
		%	daf	82.3 ± 3.3	37.5 ± 1.5	31.5 ± 1.3	32.2 ± 1.3	28.1 ± 1.1

ar—as received (working state); db—dry basis; daf—dry and ash-free basis.

following equation [22]:

$$F_n^t = \begin{cases} \min(K_{nl}s_n^t, F_n^{t-\Delta t} + K_{nu}\Delta s_n) & \text{if } \Delta s_n \geq 0 \\ \max(F_n^{t-\Delta t} + K_{nu}\Delta s_n, \lambda K_{nl}s_n^t) & \text{if } \Delta s_n < 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta s_n = s_n^t - s_n^{t-\Delta t} \quad (5)$$

where F_n^t and $F_n^{t-\Delta t}$ are the normal contact forces at the current time t and at the previous time $t - \Delta t$ respectively, Δt is the time step, Δs_n is the change in the contact normal overlap during the current time, s_n^t and $s_n^{t-\Delta t}$ are the normal overlap values at the current and previous time, respectively, K_{nl} and K_{nu} are the values of loading and unloading contact stiffnesses, respectively. Tangential contact force was calculated based on Linear spring model with Coulomb limit, it is described by the equation [22]:

$$\mathbf{F}_{tan}^t = \min\left(|\mathbf{F}_{tan,e}^t|, \mu F_n^t\right) \frac{\mathbf{F}_{tan,e}^t}{|\mathbf{F}_{tan,e}^t|} \quad (6)$$

where μ is the friction coefficient, $\mathbf{F}_{tan,e}^t$ is tangential force at the current time t treated as purely elastic. The change in particle temperature over time is calculated based on the following formula [20]:

$$m_p c_p \frac{dT_p}{dt} = \dot{Q}_p \quad (7)$$

where m_p is particle mass, c_p is the specific heat capacity for particle, T_p is particle temperature and \dot{Q}_p is a heat transfer rate into the particle. The heat transfer rate \dot{Q}_p is calculated as a sum:

$$\dot{Q}_p = \dot{Q}_{pc} + \dot{Q}_{pr} + \dot{Q}_{fp} + \Delta H_p \frac{dm_p}{dt} \quad (8)$$

where \dot{Q}_{pc} is conductive heat transfer rate for particle–particle and wall–particle interactions, \dot{Q}_{pr} is radiative heat transfer rate between particles and walls, \dot{Q}_{fp} is heat transfer rate between fluid phase and particle calculated based on the CFD model, ΔH_p is the enthalpy of pyrolysis assumed as -25 kJ/kg based on work of Haseli et al. [19]. Conductive heat transfer rate is calculated based on:

$$\dot{Q}_{pc} = 2k_c r (T_c - T_p) \quad (9)$$

where k_c is equivalent thermal conductivity of the contact, r is the radius of contact surface, T_p is particle temperature and T_c is adjacent particle or wall temperature. The model also includes radiative heat transfer between particles and walls according to equation:

$$\dot{Q}_{pr} = \frac{\sigma_b (T_i^4 - T_p^4)}{\frac{1-\epsilon_i}{\epsilon_i A_{s,i}} + \frac{1}{A_{s,j} F} + \frac{1-\epsilon_p}{\epsilon_p A_{s,p}}} \quad (10)$$

where index i refers to source surface and p refers to particle, σ_b is Stefan–Boltzmann constant, ϵ is emissivity, A_s is the surface area, F is the radiation view factor.

In the model, a uniform temperature distribution within individual particles was assumed. To evaluate the influence of biomass physical properties and process parameters on temperature uniformity within the particle, an effective Biot number was determined using effective thermal conductivity and an effective heat transfer coefficient. The effective thermal conductivity was modeled as a sum of conductive

and radiative contributions, accounting for changes in porosity, temperature, and degree of pyrolysis. The effective heat transfer coefficient was calculated as the sum of convective, conductive and radiative terms [23,24]. The effective Biot number of the biomass particle was found to lie in the range 0.3–0.5, depending on the degree of mass loss. The moderate Biot number indicates that internal temperature gradients are present but are not critical to the process. The assumption of a spatially uniform particle temperature is adopted here as a compromise between model accuracy and computational efficiency. A non-isothermal particle model will be considered in future work.

The DEM model was coupled with CFD simulation realized in Ansys Fluent software. To include presence of particles, the domain in Fluent is treated as a porous medium. The following governing equations were solved:

- mass conservation equation

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\gamma \rho_f) + \nabla \cdot (\gamma \rho_f \mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (11)$$

- momentum conservation equations

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\gamma \rho_f \mathbf{u}) + \nabla \cdot (\gamma \rho_f \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}) = -\gamma \nabla p + \nabla \cdot (\gamma \boldsymbol{\tau}) + \gamma \rho_f \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{F}_{pf} \quad (12)$$

- energy conservation equation

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\gamma \rho_f h_f) + \nabla \cdot (\gamma \rho_f \mathbf{u} h_f) = \gamma \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \gamma \boldsymbol{\tau} : \nabla \mathbf{u} - \nabla \cdot (\gamma \mathbf{q}_f) + Q_{pf} \quad (13)$$

- species transport conservation equations

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\gamma \rho Y_k) + \nabla \cdot (\gamma \rho \mathbf{u} Y_k) = -\nabla \cdot (\gamma \mathbf{J}_k) + S_{pf} \quad (14)$$

where γ is the porosity, ρ_f is the fluid density, \mathbf{u} defines the velocity vector, p is the pressure, $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is the stress tensor (which includes also the Reynolds stresses), \mathbf{g} is the vector of gravitational acceleration, \mathbf{F}_{pf} is momentum source based on particle–fluid interactions, h_f is the fluid enthalpy, \mathbf{q}_f is the heat flux. The source term Q_{pf} stands for enthalpy source due to convective heat transfer between particles and fluid, k is the species index, Y_k stands for the mass fraction of species k , \mathbf{J}_k is the diffusion flux of species k , the source term S_{pf} stands for the mass source resulting from pyrolysis. In the CFD model, it was assumed that the gas is composed of nitrogen (supplied at the inlet) and pyrolysis gas treated as a single compound representing the actual mixture, for which the average molar mass of 35 kg/kmol was determined based on [25]. The gases were treated as ideal gases.

Momentum source \mathbf{F}_{pf} in Eq. (12) is the sum of drag force and pressure gradient force:

$$\mathbf{F}_{pf} = \mathbf{F}_D + \mathbf{F}_{\nabla p} \quad (15)$$

Pressure gradient $\mathbf{F}_{\nabla p}$ equation is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\nabla p} = -V_p \nabla p \quad (16)$$

where V_p is the particle volume and ∇p stands for the local pressure gradient. Drag force in the model was calculated based on Huilin & Gidaspow [26] correlation, which is a combination of Wen & Yu [27] and Ergun [28] correlations with transition based on a blending function. The heat transfer rate between particles and fluid is calculated based on Newton's law, and the Nusselt number is calculated according to Gunn [29] correlation.

To determine the biomass pyrolysis rate in the reactor, a model based on three kinetic reactions was used. The kinetic expression takes the following form:

$$k_i = A_i e^{-\frac{E_i}{RT}} (1 - \alpha_i)^{n_i} \quad (17)$$

where the subscript i denotes the reaction number, A is pre-exponential factor, E is activation energy, R is universal gas constant, α stands for the mass loss of the component, n is the reaction order. The mass loss rate during the process is calculated as the sum of the 3 individual mass losses, each based on the respective kinetic equation of a given component, as expressed by the following equation:

$$\frac{dm_{p,i}}{dt} = -k_i c_i m_{p,i,0} \quad (18)$$

where c is a contribution coefficient, $m_{p,0}$ is an initial mass. The sum of all contribution coefficients must be equal to 1, and the total mass loss rate is

$$\frac{dm_p}{dt} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{dm_{p,i}}{dt} \quad (19)$$

The presented devolatilization model was implemented in ANSYS Rocky software as a custom module.

4. Determination of kinetic parameters

Devolatilization of the feedstock plays an important role in the pyrolysis process. Therefore, besides a global model of biomass decomposition, a multi-step model with kinetic parameters for reactions of pseudocomponents, which represent biomass constituents – hemicellulose, cellulose, lignin (and extractives in softwood) – was included. While three-step kinetic models remain widely used due to their physical interpretability and computational efficiency, several recent studies have proposed more comprehensive multistep kinetic schemes. In particular, Thoharudin et al. [30–32], proposed a comprehensive multistep kinetic mechanism. This approach satisfactorily reproduced experimental values for both pyrolysis yields and compositions. In comparison, the three-reaction kinetic model adopted in the present study represents a simplified description of the process. However, for the purposes of this work, its level of accuracy is sufficient to adequately reproduce the overall mass loss of the sample during the process. The reduced kinetic scheme offers a significantly lower computational cost, which remains important in the case of DEM–CFD modeling. Non-isothermal thermogravimetric measurements at several heating rates are typically performed for this purpose, and 3–4 parallel reactions are fitted to match the experimental data. Pseudocomponent reactions are described using the kinetic equations, e.g. first-order, n th order [33,34], iso-conversion methods [35], or with mathematical functions, such as Gaussian [36] or Asymmetric Double Sigmoidal functions [37,38]. Here n th order equations were used.

The kinetics of biomass pyrolysis was investigated by thermogravimetric analysis using the TG 209 F1 Libra instrument (NETZSCH-Gerätebau GmbH). Before analysis, the birch wood was cryo-milled to a fine powder and dried overnight at 80°C. Thermogravimetric tests were performed on a 1 mg sample under an argon atmosphere with different heating rates of 3, 6 or 12 K/min. Next, the deconvolution of the derivative of the mass loss (DTG) was conducted in Kinetic Neo 2.5 software. Three n th order reactions, corresponding to hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin, were assumed and fitted simultaneously to all three measurements, with $R^2 = 0.99987$. The kinetic parameters of the three reactions and their contribution to the overall conversion are presented in Table 3. The comparison of the conversion rates calculated with the measured data and the fitted model (Eq. (19)) is presented in Fig. 2.

The kinetic parameters obtained for the pyrolysis of individual components are consistent with values reported in the literature for wood decomposition. As shown in the DTG curves (Fig. 2), hemicellulose

Table 3

Activation energy (E_a), pre-exponential factor (k_0), and reaction order (n) of the biomass components devolatilization calculated from the deconvolution of DTG curves.

	E_a , kJ/mol	k_0 , 1/s	n	c
Hemicellulose	163.72	3.92×10^5	5.0	0.46
Cellulose	210.26	5.90×10^6	1.0	0.23
Lignin	70.72	7.68×10^1	4.1	0.31

Fig. 2. Conversion rate (DTG) from the measurements and from the fitted n th order reactions, calculated according to Eqs. (17), (18) and (19).

decomposition peaks between 220–300 °C, cellulose undergoes rapid degradation in a sharp step around 350 °C, and lignin devolatilizes gradually, exhibiting a broad, low-intensity peak over the entire mass-loss range. These temperature ranges fall well within those summarized by Shen et al. [39]. They investigated birch and fir wood and reported activation energies of 148 and 212 kJ/mol, respectively, for hemicellulose, 157 and 167 kJ/mol for cellulose, and 121 and 166 kJ/mol for lignin. Similarly, Kim et al. [34] reported activation energies of 110 and 109 kJ/mol for hemicellulose in pine and birch, respectively, 193 and 232 kJ/mol for cellulose, and 35 and 27 kJ/mol for lignin. The results obtained in the present study are in good agreement with these literature values. The wide dispersion of kinetic parameters reported for lignin decomposition can be attributed to the heterogeneous nature of this polymer and its broad decomposition temperature range.

5. Computational procedure and validation of the numerical model

To validate the numerical model, simulations of the pyrolysis reactor operation were carried out under the same conditions as the experimental tests. All the simulations were conducted as a transient analysis. In DEM-based modeling, particularly in coupled DEM–CFD simulations, high computational cost remains a major limitation, as also noted by Attanayake [18]. The computational demand arises from tracking individual particles and their interactions, combined with the significantly smaller DEM time step compared to transient CFD. As a result, the computational time increases nearly linearly with the number of tracked particles. In the present study, DEM calculations were performed on a GPU (NVIDIA Quadro RTX 8000), while CFD simulations ran in parallel on a 40-core Intel Xeon Gold 6242R CPU, with data exchange after each CFD time step. The model tracked up

Fig. 3. Geometry of the numerical model.

Fig. 4. Numerical mesh of the CFD model.

to approximately 1100 particles, resulting in computation times of 1–2 days depending on the case. For systems involving substantially larger particle numbers, a Coarse-Grain Model is recommended, in which larger particles are used which represent a specific group of smaller real particles.

The geometry of the model includes the biomass inlet, the interior of the reactor with the auger, and ends at the point where the auger terminates. The geometry is shown in Fig. 3. The computational mesh of the CFD model consists of approximately 124,000 elements, 99.8% of which are hexahedral. The remaining elements are of the wedge type. The minimum orthogonality in the mesh is 0.23, while the average orthogonality is 0.83. The maximum aspect ratio is 8.2, and the average value is 1.7. The mesh is shown in Fig. 4.

The mesh size was selected in accordance with the applied numerical method. In coupled DEM–CFD modeling, it is recommended that the mesh element size be of the same order of magnitude as or larger than the particle size used in the DEM model. Such a recommendation is provided in the software documentation [20]. Nevertheless, a mesh sensitivity analysis of the CFD model was performed by carrying out unsteady simulations using 2 finer meshes with 225,000 and 525,000 elements. Temperature evolution at two locations was monitored, showing agreement between both meshes with average differences below 1%. Mean heat flow rate profiles at the walls were also compared, yielding agreement at approximately 4%. In this case, the largest differences were observed at the beginning of the process, when a significant peak in heat flow rate occurred. After a few seconds of simulation, the agreement improved to below 1%. Based on these, the selected mesh size was considered appropriate.

The boundary conditions of the model were selected to accurately replicate the experimental conditions. The boundary conditions are summarized in Table 4. Conditions for the CFD model and for the DEM model are provided separately, as these were two models operated separately in coupling mode. Similarly to the experiment, the biomass was fed in portions every 2 or 4 min, depending on the case analyzed.

The simulation results were compared with the experimental data and are presented in Table 5. The parameter being compared is the percentage loss of volatile matter mass in the biomass, which, for the experimental data, was calculated based on the analyses summarized previously in Table 2. All numerical results are overpredicted relative to the measurements; however, the maximum relative error, observed in the first case, remains small at 5.18%. The Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) for the analyzed cases is 3.43 percentage points. As expected, the calculated mass loss is greater for a longer residence time. It can be observed that with an increase in the feeding rate, the mass loss predicted in the simulation decreases slightly. This result is consistent with expectations, since with greater reactor filling, heat transfer from the walls to the interior of the bed is hindered, and a decrease in pyrolysis efficiency in the reactor can be expected. More complex conclusions can be drawn from the experimental work. For both feeding rates the increase in residence time resulted in the increased ash content and decreased volatile matter content, which is consistent with the increased devolatilization of the biomass, and the simulation results. Comparison of the lower and higher feeding rates shows that the increased load of the biomass resulted in the decreased ash content and, interestingly, decreased volatile matter content. The decreased ash content suggests that more carbon remained in the char, which is consistent with the simulation and suggest lower devolatilization of the char. It can be caused by the heat transfer hindrance, but the other contributing factor might be the enhanced secondary volatiles reforming, due to diffusion limitations and longer residence time within the thicker layer of char, as noted by numerous authors, such as [40,41]. This second phenomenon also explains the lower volatile matter content in the char from the higher feeding rate tests. During secondary volatile reforming, i.e. volatiles–char interactions, the aromatic compounds polymerize on the char surface (increasing the overall C content in the char—thus decreasing ash content). Prolonging the polymerization (aka coking) of volatiles on the char surface enhances the accompanying dehydrogenation and demethylation reactions, where the more labile

Table 4
Boundary conditions used in the model, listed individually for the CFD and DEM.

Boundary:	Model	Boundary condition	Value	Unit
Tube wall	CFD	Fixed temperature	500	°C
	DEM	Fixed temperature	500	°C
Remaining walls	CFD	Adiabatic	–	–
	DEM	Adiabatic	–	–
Inlet	CFD	N ₂ mass flow inlet	1.97×10^{-6} - 1.79×10^{-5}	kg/s
	DEM	Mass inlet	7.83×10^{-3} - 1.88×10^{-2}	kg/portion
Outlet	CFD	Pressure outlet	101 325	Pa
	DEM	Escape	–	–

Table 5
Comparison of the experimental and simulation results.

Case	Residence time, min	Mean feeding rate, kg/s	Mass loss of volatiles, %		Relative error, %
			Measurement	Simulation	
1	6	1.96×10^{-4}	86.8	91.3	5.18
2	12	9.79×10^{-5}	89.9	93.9	4.45
3	6	4.70×10^{-4}	88.9	90.8	2.14
4	12	2.35×10^{-4}	90.9	93.6	2.97

Fig. 5. Velocity profile and streamlines, with the streamlines displayed in a uniform green color for clarity, results for case 3 (6 min. residence time and higher feeding rate).

aromatic species become more strongly attached to the primary carbon matrix. Thus, while the overall C content increases due to fixed carbon agglomeration, the volatile matter content decreases as the coke layer becomes more stable. Notably, the numerical model does not account for the secondary reactions or the energetic effects of pyrolysis, and therefore such an effect could not be captured in the simulation. This indicates the need for further development of the numerical model in the future to obtain more precise results.

6. Detailed results

The obtained results were subjected to a detailed comparative analysis aimed at determining the influence of process conditions on gas flow, temperature profiles, and the conversion of biomass components into the gas phase. In the actual reactor, only a minimal gap is maintained between the auger and the walls to prevent material from accumulating at the bottom. However, in the numerical model, this gap was omitted, resulting in no flow path between the auger and the walls. Such a simplification is justified, as the components in the actual reactor are fitted so tightly that the auger cannot operate at ambient temperature. Only after heating the system to the operating temperature the rotational motion of the auger becomes possible, however, physical contact between its outer surface and the reactor wall is maintained throughout operation. Consequently, the gas moves entirely in a rotational pattern around the auger shaft. Fig. 5 shows streamlines and contours of gas velocity within the reactor for one selected case. An increase in gas velocity along the reactor can be observed, which is caused by both the temperature rise and the mass source from the volatile release during biomass pyrolysis.

The temperature of the particles (in the DEM model) is shown in Fig. 6 for a case with a 6-min residence time and higher reactor filling.

Differences in temperature can be observed for particles located close to each other in the reactor. The figure also shows the temperature profile in gas phase (CFD model). It can be observed that the gas heats up rapidly due to contact with the reactor walls. It is also evident that in regions where the biomass bed is present, the temperature rise is lower due to the thermal resistance of the biomass bed. In contrast, in regions where the gas flows directly along the reactor walls (e.g., at the upper surface of the reactor), gas heating is more intense.

Fig. 7 shows the temperature profiles for selected particles as they move through the reactor in the analyzed cases. The profiles were generated for the particles with the highest temperature increase among all particles in the given case. It can be observed that the temperature profiles for the residence time of 12 min and different reactor fillings are almost identical, whereas in the case of the shorter residence time of 6 min, the temperature increase is greater for the higher reactor filling. Since a greater temperature increase was observed in the case with higher reactor filling, it can be assumed that this is the effect of the insulating properties of the biomass leading to higher temperature differences in the bed. To verify this, in further analysis, temperature profiles were compared for a group of 11 randomly selected particles in each case. The results for 6 min residence time cases are presented in Fig. 8. In the case of higher reactor filling, the temperature spread is greater when compared to the case with lower filling. Specifically, for the data presented, the standard deviation of temperature is 21.8 K for the higher filling (case 3) and 16.5 K for the lower filling (case 1). Compared to the cases with a longer residence time of 12 min, the temperature standard deviation is 5.6 K for the lower filling (case 2) and 13.6 K for the higher filling (case 4). Summarizing, an increase in the temperature variability of the particles is observed with increasing filling, but also with decreasing residence time in the reactor. The

Fig. 6. Temperature field of gas phase in the CFD model (top) and temperature of particles in the DEM model (bottom), case 3 (6 min residence time and higher filling).

Fig. 7. Temperature profiles along the reactor for selected particle in analyzed cases.

temperature variability is an important parameter in reactor design because, with improperly selected process parameters, it may not be possible to achieve the required degree of conversion for some part of biomass particles. Therefore it is desirable to maintain low particle temperature variability. Although the standard deviations of the temperature are relatively low, though they can affect the mass release rate, as will be discussed below.

Fig. 9 shows the relative content of volatile components in particles along the reactor for the analyzed cases. It illustrates how the previously mentioned temperature differences affect the distribution of volatiles in the particles along the reactor. The largest spread is observed in the case with the largest temperature variations, corresponding to the shorter residence time of 6 min and higher reactor filling. The non-uniformity decreases towards the end of the reactor, but not completely, especially when the residence time is shorter. Fig. 10 presents the standard deviations of the relative content along the reactor. While all cases tend toward a uniform relative content at the reactor outlet, noticeable differences remain. The maximum standard deviation observed is 8.4×10^{-3} (6 min, higher filling), whereas the minimum is 1.2×10^{-3} (12 min, lower filling).

The intensity of the pyrolysis process depends directly on the particle temperature. Fig. 11 presents the mass loss rate of particles in the reactor for case with 6 min residence time and higher feeding rate (case 3). A significant increase in the rate of mass loss is observed

at the beginning of the reactor. Fig. 12 shows the mass loss in total and divided into components (cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin) for selected particles in the four analyzed cases. The plots represent the particles with the highest mass loss in each case. According to the TGA measurements (see Fig. 2), the highest devolatilization rate is obtained in the range of approximately 500–620 K, thus, the highest mass losses are observed in the regions where the particles reach this temperature level. The mass loss is similar in all analyzed cases, with the highest value observed for the case with a 6-minute residence time and higher reactor filling. Although it may appear that devolatilization is practically completed in the second half of the reactor, it should be noted that, due to the existing non-uniformities, continued exposure of the material to a high-temperature environment is necessary to obtain a sufficiently uniform final product. Fig. 13 shows the mass of individual fractions representing cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin, thereby visualizing the differences in mass loss among these components.

The standard deviations of mass loss divided into cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin were calculated. These data, together with the standard deviation of temperature, are presented in Table 6. A direct relationship between variability of temperature and the mass loss of individual components is evident. The highest standard deviation of mass loss was achieved in case 3 with shorter residence time and higher filling of the reactor. This confirms the conclusion that the heat-transfer conditions in the reactor directly affect the quality of the obtained product, not only in terms of the average yield of products (solid, liquid and gaseous) from the biomass feed, but also in terms of the non-uniform biomass conversion. When designing an auger reactor for pyrolysis, particular attention should be paid to the appropriate combination of residence time and biomass feeding rate in order to obtain a product with the desired level of non-uniformity. Due to differences in reactor configurations (e.g., diameter, auger pitch, and rotational speed), universal operating parameters cannot be defined even for a given type of biomass. Therefore, detailed analyses are required, for which the DEM–CFD method is particularly advantageous, as it enables the quantification of non-uniformity of the relevant process parameters.

7. Conclusions

A coupled DEM–CFD model was developed for the simulation of heat transfer and pyrolysis processes in an auger reactor. The model can support the design and scale-up of auger reactors by enabling the assessment of the impact of heat transfer conditions on process performance.

Fig. 8. Temperature profiles of random particles in case 1–6 min and lower filling (left) and case 3–6 min and higher filling (right).

Fig. 9. Content of volatiles in the individual particles within the reactor for analyzed cases - 6 min and lower filling (top left), 12 min and lower filling (top right), 6 min and higher filling (bottom left), 12 min and higher filling (bottom right).

Table 6
Average standard deviation of selected parameters along the reactor.

Case	Residence time, min	Filling	Standard deviation			
			Temperature, K	Cellulose mass loss rate, kg/s $\times 10^{-8}$	Hemicellulose mass loss rate, kg/s $\times 10^{-8}$	Lignin mass loss rate, kg/s $\times 10^{-8}$
1	6	lower	16.5	7.15	5.54	1.87
2	12	lower	5.6	1.83	1.69	0.65
3	6	higher	21.8	8.83	7.24	2.43
4	12	higher	13.6	4.16	3.53	1.26

Fig. 10. Standard deviations of volatile content in particles along the reactor.

Validation was carried out based on experimental measurements conducted in a laboratory-scale reactor. Four different operating conditions were analyzed. The presented model demonstrates sufficient accuracy to be used for analyzing the influence of process parameters on the heating rate of individual bed particles and the intensity of the pyrolysis process in the reactor.

The analysis of the results indicated that both an increase in reactor filling and a reduction in residence time lead to greater nonuniformity in particles temperature, which directly translates into nonuniformity in mass loss. Significant differences in process evolution were observed among the analyzed cases. A noticeable differences in volatile content within the particle population was identified, associated with temperature variations. Ultimately, all cases were approaching to the same point—complete devolatilization, however, a certain spread of parameters at the reactor outlet was still observed. Consequently, if process parameters are not properly selected, nonuniform conversion of individual biomass particles may occur in the reactor. Simulations using the DEM–CFD method, in which heat-transfer and pyrolysis processes are modeled within individual particles in the bed, allows to determine the nonuniformity of conversion in the reactor.

Fig. 11. Particle mass loss rate due to the pyrolysis process in the reactor, case 3 (6 min residence time and higher filling).

Fig. 12. Mass loss of selected particles within the reactor for analyzed cases - 6 min and lower filling (top left), 12 min and lower filling (top right), 6 min and higher filling (bottom left), 12 min and higher filling (bottom right).

Fig. 13. Mass of individual fractions in the particles, from top to bottom: cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin; case 3 (6 min residence time and higher filling).

Presented model can be successfully applied in the design process and upscaling of this type of reactors, however, it should be noted that increasing the number of tracked particles will significantly increase the computation time, which may require simplifications, such as using parcels in the model to represent groups of actual particles of the same properties.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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